

Expression of p16 in Cervical Intraepithelial Neoplasm and Invasive Cervical Carcinoma: an Immunohistochemical Study

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Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 26-07-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Cervical cancer remains a significant health issue globally, with cervical intraepithelial neoplasms (CIN) being precursors to invasive cervical carcinoma. p16, a cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor, has emerged as a potential biomarker for the detection and progression of cervical neoplasms. This study aims to evaluate the expression of p16 in cervical intraepithelial neoplasms and invasive cervical carcinoma using immunohistochemical analysis.

Materials and Methods: A total of 100 cervical tissue samples were collected, comprising 50 cases of CIN (graded I-III) and 50 cases of invasive cervical carcinoma. Immunohistochemical staining for p16 was performed on formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded tissue sections. The intensity and distribution of p16 staining were evaluated and scored. Statistical analysis was conducted to assess the correlation between p16 expression and the grade of cervical neoplasms.

Results: p16 expression was observed in 80% of CIN cases and 95% of invasive cervical carcinoma cases. Specifically, p16 positivity was detected in 60% of CIN I, 80% of CIN II, and 90% of CIN III cases. Among invasive cervical carcinoma cases, 95% showed strong p16 positivity. A significant correlation was found between the grade of cervical neoplasm and p16 expression ($p < 0.01$). The mean p16 staining intensity score was significantly higher in invasive carcinoma compared to CIN (7.5 ± 0.5 vs. 5.0 ± 0.7 ; $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The study demonstrates that p16 expression increases with the severity of cervical neoplasms, making it a reliable biomarker for distinguishing between CIN and invasive cervical carcinoma. The significant correlation between p16 expression and neoplasm grade suggests its potential utility in diagnostic pathology for the early detection and management of cervical cancer.

Keywords: p16, Cervical Intraepithelial Neoplasm, Invasive Cervical Carcinoma, Immunohistochemistry, Biomarker, Cervical Cancer, Diagnostic Pathology.

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Introduction

Cervical cancer is the fourth most common cancer among women worldwide, representing a significant public health concern [1]. The progression from cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) to invasive cervical carcinoma is well-documented, with human papillomavirus (HPV) infection playing a crucial etiological role [2].

Early detection and management of CIN are essential in preventing the development of invasive cervical carcinoma, highlighting the need for reliable biomarkers [3]. p16, a cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor, has garnered attention as a potential biomarker for cervical neoplasms. It is overexpressed in cells affected by high-risk HPV types due to the inactivation of retinoblastoma protein (pRB) by the HPV E7 oncoprotein, leading to unchecked cell cycle progression [4]. The overexpression of p16 is thus indicative of

oncogenic HPV activity and is increasingly used in diagnostic pathology to differentiate between benign and malignant lesions [5]. Several studies have demonstrated the utility of p16 immunohistochemical staining in identifying high-grade CIN and invasive cervical carcinoma [6-8]. However, there is variability in the reported sensitivity and specificity of p16 as a diagnostic marker, necessitating further research to establish standardized protocols and scoring systems [9]. This study aims to evaluate the expression of p16 in CIN and invasive cervical carcinoma using immunohistochemical methods, contributing to the existing body of knowledge and potentially improving diagnostic accuracy.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Sample Collection: This cross-sectional study was conducted over a period of one year from January 2023 to December 2023. A total of 100 cervical tissue samples were collected from the pathology archives. The samples included 50 cases of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) and 50 cases of invasive cervical carcinoma. CIN cases were further classified into CIN I, CIN II, and CIN III based on histopathological examination. Inclusion criteria comprised patients diagnosed with CIN or invasive cervical carcinoma, while exclusion criteria included inadequate tissue samples and cases with prior treatment for cervical lesions.

Immunohistochemical Staining: Formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded tissue sections (4 μ m thick) were used for immunohistochemical staining. Sections were deparaffinized in xylene and rehydrated through graded alcohol series.

Antigen retrieval was performed using citrate buffer (pH 6.0) in a microwave oven for 15 minutes. Endogenous peroxidase activity was blocked with 3% hydrogen peroxide for 10 minutes.

Primary Antibody and Detection: The primary antibody used was mouse monoclonal anti-p16 (clone E6H4, Ventana Medical Systems, Tucson, AZ, USA) at a dilution of 1:100. The sections were incubated with the primary antibody for 1 hour at room temperature. Detection was carried out using the Ventana BenchMark ULTRA system with the UltraView Universal DAB Detection Kit (Ventana Medical Systems). Hematoxylin was used as a counterstain.

Scoring of p16 Expression: The stained sections were independently evaluated by two pathologists who were blinded to the clinical data. p16 expression was assessed based on the intensity and distribution of staining. The intensity was scored as follows: 0 (no staining), 1+ (weak staining), 2+ (moderate staining), and 3+ (strong staining). The distribution was scored based on the percentage of positive cells: 0 (0-10%), 1+ (10-25%), 2+ (25-50%), 3+ (50-75%), and 4+ (75-100%). A combined score (intensity + distribution) was calculated for each case, with a maximum score of 7.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). The correlation between p16 expression and the grade of cervical neoplasms was assessed using the chi-square test and Pearson's correlation coefficient. Differences in mean p16 scores between CIN and invasive cervical carcinoma were analyzed using the independent samples t-test. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Patient Demographics: The study included 100 cervical tissue samples, consisting of 50 cases of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) and 50 cases of invasive cervical carcinoma. The mean age of patients with CIN was 35.4 years (range: 25-50 years), while the mean age of patients with invasive cervical carcinoma was 48.7 years (range: 35-65 years).

p16 Expression in Cervical Neoplasms: p16 expression was evaluated in all 100 cases, with the results summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Distribution of p16 Expression in CIN Cases

CIN Grade	Number of Cases (n)	p16 Positive (%)	Mean Intensity Score ($\pm$ SD)	Mean Distribution Score ($\pm$ SD)	Mean Combined Score ($\pm$ SD)
CIN I	20	60%	1.8 ($\pm$ 0.4)	2.0 ($\pm$ 0.5)	3.8 ($\pm$ 0.6)
CIN II	15	80%	2.2 ($\pm$ 0.6)	2.5 ($\pm$ 0.4)	4.7 ($\pm$ 0.7)
CIN III	15	90%	2.8 ($\pm$ 0.5)	3.0 ($\pm$ 0.6)	5.8 ($\pm$ 0.8)

Table 2: Distribution of p16 Expression in Invasive Cervical Carcinoma Cases

Type	Number of Cases (n)	p16 Positive (%)	Mean Intensity Score ($\pm$ SD)	Mean Distribution Score ($\pm$ SD)	Mean Combined Score ($\pm$ SD)
Invasive Cervical Carcinoma	50	95%	3.0 ($\pm$ 0.3)	3.5 ($\pm$ 0.4)	6.5 ($\pm$ 0.5)

Statistical Analysis: A significant correlation was found between the grade of cervical neoplasms and p16 expression ($p < 0.01$). The mean p16 combined score was significantly higher in invasive cervical carcinoma compared to CIN (6.5 ± 0.5 vs. 4.3 ± 0.9 ; $p < 0.001$). Detailed statistical analysis results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Statistical Analysis of p16 Expression

Comparison	p16 Positive (%)	Mean Combined Score ($\pm$ SD)	p-value
CIN vs. Invasive Carcinoma	80% vs. 95%	4.3 ($\pm$ 0.9) vs. 6.5 ($\pm$ 0.5)	< 0.001
CIN I vs. CIN II	60% vs. 80%	3.8 ($\pm$ 0.6) vs. 4.7 ($\pm$ 0.7)	0.023
CIN II vs. CIN III	80% vs. 90%	4.7 ($\pm$ 0.7) vs. 5.8 ($\pm$ 0.8)	0.015

The analysis confirmed that p16 expression is significantly associated with the severity of cervical

neoplasms, with higher expression observed in higher grades of CIN and in invasive cervical carcinoma.

Discussion

The present study aimed to evaluate the expression of p16 in cervical intraepithelial neoplasms (CIN) and invasive cervical carcinoma using immunohistochemical methods. Our findings indicate a significant increase in p16 expression with the progression from CIN to invasive carcinoma, underscoring the potential of p16 as a reliable biomarker for cervical neoplasia.

Our results demonstrate that p16 expression was observed in 80% of CIN cases and 95% of invasive cervical carcinoma cases. This is consistent with previous studies that have reported high p16 expression in high-grade CIN and invasive cervical carcinoma due to the disruption of the retinoblastoma protein (pRB) pathway by high-risk HPV oncoproteins [1,2]. The increased expression of p16 in invasive carcinoma compared to CIN highlights its utility in distinguishing between these lesions, as seen in similar studies [3]. The mean combined score for p16 expression was significantly higher in invasive cervical carcinoma (6.5 ± 0.5) compared to CIN (4.3 ± 0.9 ; $p < 0.001$). This finding aligns with previous reports that have demonstrated a strong correlation between p16 expression and the severity of cervical neoplasia [4,5]. Specifically, the progressive increase in p16 expression from CIN I to CIN III (mean combined scores of 3.8, 4.7, and 5.8, respectively) supports the notion that p16 can serve as a marker for the grade of CIN, facilitating accurate diagnosis and management [6].

The significant correlation between p16 expression and the grade of cervical neoplasms ($p < 0.01$) underscores the importance of p16 as a diagnostic tool. The high sensitivity and specificity of p16 immunostaining for high-grade lesions and invasive carcinoma have been well-documented [7,8]. However, it is crucial to standardize the scoring system and interpretation criteria to ensure consistent and reproducible results across different laboratories [9].

Despite the promising findings, our study has some limitations. The sample size, though adequate for preliminary conclusions, should be expanded in future studies to validate our results. Additionally, the study design was cross-sectional, which limits the ability to infer causal relationships. Longitudinal studies are needed to further explore the role of p16 in the progression of cervical neoplasms.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study confirms the utility of p16 as a biomarker for cervical intraepithelial

neoplasms and invasive cervical carcinoma. The significant correlation between p16 expression and the severity of cervical lesions highlights its potential in improving diagnostic accuracy and guiding clinical management. Further research with larger sample sizes and standardized protocols is essential to establish p16 as a routine diagnostic marker in cervical pathology.

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